

Results & Outputs

Transforming Research through Innovative
Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

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The TRIPLE (“Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration”) project is financed under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, Grant agreement ID 863420, for a duration of 42 months (2019–2023). TRIPLE consists of a consortium of 22 partners from 15 European countries and is coordinated from France by the Research Infrastructure Huma-Num, a unit of the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS).

The content of this brochure reflects only TRIPLE’s view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Introduction

The TRIPLE project started in October 2019 with the vision of empowering European researchers in the area of social sciences and humanities (SSH) to collaborate, discover and share resources without disciplinary or linguistic barriers. The TRIPLE team, composed of about 90 people, designed an open and accessible platform to showcase European research results from a wide spectrum of disciplines and national communities and hence increase their visibility and social impact.

The result is the GoTriple discovery platform, built according to the principles of transparency, interoperability, and user-centred design. The platform is specifically tailored to the SSH community. It offers a single point of access to the largest European collections of scientific publications and other resources. Moreover, GoTriple is multilingual and allows users to search and retrieve results in 11 European languages.

Users can also have easy access to several additional functionalities: visualisation of search results, crowdfunding, annotations, personalised recommendations and a trust-based social network.

The platform will continue to serve as a hub for discovering research resources and peers, as well as a meeting place for researchers and a starting point for innovative ways of conducting and contextualising research. GoTriple is one of the core services of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure. After the end of the project, the platform will be sustainably governed, supported and upgraded by a multi-stakeholder Governance Board.

In the course of designing and building the GoTriple discovery platform, TRIPLE's closely-knit, diverse community of international partners has produced a range of other resources that will be of use to researchers, developers, programmers, librarians, students, and other stakeholders in the

fields of social sciences, humanities, arts, and open science in general. Whether you wish to reuse the technical building blocks of the platform or are looking for training in open science, the following sections will provide you with helpful links and recommendations. This booklet provides only an overview of the main achievements of the TRIPLE pro-

ject and the features of the GoTriple platform. Readers are however cordially invited to explore the links below and learn more about TRIPLE's resources.

The TRIPLE team thanks you for your support and interest. We hope that GoTriple will soon become one of your favourite research tools.

Suzanne Dumouchel,
Project coordinator

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the European Research Area for social sciences and humanities (SSH). Its mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH.

OPERAS' aim is to make Open Science a reality for research in the SSH and achieve a scholarly communication system where knowledge produced in the SSH benefits researchers, academics, students and more generally the whole society across Europe and worldwide, without barriers.

OPERAS services catalogue

The OPERAS Research Infrastructure is developing a portfolio of different scholarly communication services at European level. Although diverse in nature, OPERAS' services are designed according to the overall mission of

the federation: they pool, aggregate, or federate existing resources from across Europe to provide European researchers with a single point of access to a full range of European-wide resources rather than fragmented local ones. With the development of its services, OPERAS is building transnational access to scholarly communication resources for researchers across the European Research Area and integrating the services into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) marketplace. GoTriple is the core discovery service, complemented by services for analytics, quality assurance, and research for society services.

operas-eu.org

GoTriple is...

an innovative multilingual discovery solution for the social sciences and humanities (SSH). It provides a single access point for discovering research artefacts that are relevant to the wide variety of disciplines under the

umbrella domain of SSH: publications and research data, project descriptions and researcher profiles. These are automatically imported from aggregators, semantically enriched and linked in GoTriple. Users will also have access to a number of additional innovative tools and applications.

As of December 2022, GoTriple BETA offers...

4,3+ million publications

112,000+ data sets

2.8 million authors and 170 users' profiles

10 aggregators and providers

27 SSH disciplines

3,300+ SSH concepts

11 languages

5 innovative services

GoTriple Facts & Numbers

GoTriple scheme

GoTriple allows you to...

- Browse, find, access and reuse scholarly SSH resources currently distributed across local, language- and discipline-specific repositories
- Visualise your search results
- Find personalised recommendations
- Annotate web documents
- Find and connect with other researchers and projects across disciplinary, cultural and language boundaries
- Explore new ways of funding research

Impacts of GoTriple...

- Reconnecting culture and science
- Strengthening ties between research, industry and society
- Increasing (re)use of SSH research
- Stimulating inter- disciplinary & cross-cultural collaborations
- Uniting fragmentary access to SSH resources
- Enhancing linguistic and cultural diversity in Europe
- Contributing to the objectives of Open Science
- Supporting scientific, industrial and societal applications of SSH research
- Devising new ways to discover, conduct and connect research

Coming in 2023

Addition of national and European providers and aggregators, including:

- Europeana
- BASE

to complement Isidore, DOAJ, DOAB, OOpen, OpenAI-RE, Biblioteka Nauki, EKT, ZRC SAZU, Coimbra University, CESSDA, OpenEdition, CLARIN, and EconStor.

The GoTriple platform is designed on the principles of open science and utmost transparency. The technical resources will be of interest to developers and others working in the

fields of digital humanities, research infrastructures, and information and communication technology.

GoTriple APIs

<https://api.gotriple.eu/>

GoTriple Vocabulary

<https://www.semantics.gr/authorities/vocabularies/SSH-LCSH>

During the course of the project, the TRIPLE team organised a range of events to confer with the scientific community and share their

own progress. The exchange of findings, ideas, and opinions was invaluable at the time and may support future endeavours.

TRIPLE ThatCamps

#1: Discovering Discovery

#2: Scientific Crowdfunding

#3: Sustainability in Open Science

1st TRIPLE International Conference

Empowering Discovery in Open Social Sciences and Humanities

22–24 November 2022

2nd International TRIPLE Conference

Improving Discovery and Collaboration in Open Science

1–3 February 2023

Hackathon

#1: Library of Congress Subject Headings in the GoTriple vocabulary

#2: APIs of GoTriple (scheduled for Feb. 2023)

Read more in TRIPLE Deliverable 6.6: API's Development-RP3: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7371831>.

Crowdfunding is one of the innovative services of GoTriple, offering an alternative funding system – and more - to researchers from all disciplines and levels of experience.

Crowdfunding Initiative

OPERAS Crowdfunding Channel

Workshops

Resources

The TRIPLE project recognized the need for training in topics related to the GoTriple platform in particular, open science skills in general, and current issues in the digital humanities. Researchers and educators alike will be able to explore the topics in depth and reuse the material for their own training events.

- The linked data ecosystem for SSH and a case study from the cultural heritage domain
- Multilingual Vocabularies for the Social Sciences and Humanities
- FAIR Data in Social Sciences and Humanities
- The Open Access Publishing Platform Open Research Europe (ORE)
- Rights of Data Subjects in Language Resources
- Copyright and Academia in the Digital Era
- TRIPLE Training toolkit: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7309919>

For a full list of training workshops and materials, see the [TRIPLE Open Science Training Series](#). Training materials are also available on [DARIAH Campus](#).

TRIPLE Training
Toolkit

Training Series

DARIAH Campus

Achenbach K, Błaszczczyńska M, De Paoli S et al. Defining discovery: Is Google Scholar a discovery platform? An essay on the need for a new approach to scholarly discovery [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. *Open Res Europe* 2022, 2:28. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14318.2>

Balula, Ana & Delfim Leão (2021): Multilingualism within Scholarly Communication in SSH: A literature review. In: *Italian Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science (JLIS.it)* 12(2), 88–98. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4403/jlis.it-12672>

Dumouchel, Suzanne, Francesca Di Donato, Monica Monachini, Yoann Moranville, Stefanie Pohle & Maria Eskevich (2020): Social Sciences and Humanities Pathway Towards the European Open Science Cloud. In: Daan Broeder, Maria Eskevich & Monica Monachini (eds.), *Proceedings of the Workshop about Language Resources for the SSH Cloud Language Resources and Evaluation Conference (LREC)*, 11–16 May 2020, Marseille [cancelled due to COVID-19]. Marseille, France: European Language Resources Association, 5–9. Zenodo. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3898443>

Mathiak, Brigitte , Nick Juty, Alessia Bardi, Julien Colomb & Peter Kraker (2021): *Discoverability Use Cases to help define Requirements for Research Data Discovery Tools* [preprint submitted to the CODATA Data Science Journal]. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5833952> (supplementary material: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5211196> (dataset))

For a full list of TRIPLE project publications and deliverables, visit the [project page](#).

Planned and expected developments of the GoTriple platform in the future include

- User interface in national languages, starting with French and Italian
- Integration of new data sources
- Better presentation of data
- Continued improvements of the data quality with new keywords
- Integration with OPERAS' Mattermost as a messaging system
- Continued developments and upgrades after the end of the TRIPLE project

Stay tuned! Visit [GoTriple](https://gotriple.eu) and subscribe to [OPERAS newsletter](#).

What comes next?

The success of the TRIPLE project would not be possible without the dedicated collaboration of the project partners.

Max Weber Foundation

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German Humanities Institutes Abroad

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open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities

Institute for Computational Linguistics «Antonio Zampolli» NATIONAL RESEARCH COUNCIL OF ITALY

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Project Partners

